

What Remains Challenging to Simulate Historical Ocean Deoxygenation?

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Revised Version

Introduction: Observed Historical Global Deoxygenation

$\Delta O_{2,Inv}$ [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

World Ocean Database 2013 [Ito et al., 2017]

OHC [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

ECMWF ORA-S4 [Balmaseda, et al., 2014]

O₂-Heat Ratio [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

- Observed global deoxygenation and ocean heat uptake in the past decades [e.g. *Schmidtke et al., 2017*]
- Strong negative correlation between $O_{2,Inv}$ and OHC (regression coefficient: -8.2 nmol/J) [Ito et al., 2017]
- Models underestimate the dissolved oxygen loss compared to the observations [e.g. *Oschlies et al., 2018*]

What are the Gaps?

- Internal variability and forced response: atmospheric forcing for ocean biogeochemical cycles.
→ Observed low-frequency climate variability matters? : OMIP
- Model's back ground mean states (i.e. spin-up states).
→ How ocean physics and biogeochemistry respond to forcing? : OMIP and CMIP6
- Model's structural uncertainties (i.e. ocean biogeochemical schemes)
- Uncertainties in observations
(also discussed in another CRESCENDO contributions, *Takano and Ilyina, 2021 (in revision)*)
→ Insufficient data coverage, interpolation scheme, database, etc.

Ocean Model Intercomparison Project (OMIP) and CMIP6 Simulations

- Focusing on **upper ocean [0-700m] global** O_{2,Inv} (Oxygen Inventory) and OHC (Ocean Heat Content).
- Mainly focusing on discussing O_{2,Inv} and OHC changes after **1950s-**, **ensemble mean perspectives**.
- We will introduce comparison between models and observational dataset for transient O_{2,Inv}.

Simulated Deoxygenation and OHU (Ocean Heat Uptake)

$\Delta O_2, Inv$ [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

MM-MEAN Quasi Global Integrated Dissolved Oxygen Inventory 0-700m

OHC [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

MM-MEAN Quasi Global Integrated Ocean Heat Content 0-700m

The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2)

Changes in Oxygen Saturation and Apparent Oxygen Utilization

*The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2)
Apparent Oxygen Utilization: AOU*

Patterns of Deoxygenation and Ocean Heat Uptake

~ 50 years linear trend

$\Delta O_2, Inv$ [0-700m]

OHC [0-700m]

*Linear trend from 1958-2009 (1968-2018), approximately 50-year trend
The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2)*

Drivers of Ocean Deoxygenation

$\Delta O_{2,sat} Inv [0-700m]$

~ 50 years linear trend

$$O_2 = O_{2,sat}(\theta, S) - AOU$$

AOU Inv [0-700m]

Linear trend from 1958-2009 (1968-2018), approximately 50-year trend
The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2)

Comparison with The Observations

Temporal Data Coverage Pattern

Fractional Volume Coverage

World Ocean Database 2013: Data Coverage Information [Ito et al., 2017]

Observationally sub-sample model output, grid volume normalized following the observational scaling from Ito's paper

$$I_{O_2}(t) = \left(\frac{V_{obs}(t)}{V_{tot}} \right)^{-1} \int O'_2(\mathbf{x}, t) dV$$

Comparison with The Observations: Deoxygenation and OHC

Volume Normalized $\Delta O_2, Inv$ [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

OHC [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

MM-MEAN Normalized Quasi Global Integrated Dissolved Oxygen Inventory 0-700m

MM-MEAN Quasi Global Integrated Ocean Heat Content 0-700m

*The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2)
O₂ inventory, volume normalized based on observational dataset*

Comparison with The Observations: O₂-Heat Ratio

O₂-Heat Ratio [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

O₂Inv decrease: OMIP1 < OMIP2 << CMIP6 < Obs
 → attributes to AOU changes

OHC decrease: OMIP models << CMIP6, Obs
 → impact on oxygen solubility changes

*The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2)
 O₂ inventory, volume normalized based on observational dataset*

Insights from CRESCENDO Ocean Simulations

$\Delta O_2, \text{Inv}$ [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

OHC [0-700m] [70°S-65°N]

MM-MEAN Quasi Global Integrated Dissolved Oxygen Inventory 0-700m

MM-MEAN Quasi Global Integrated Ocean Heat Content 0-700m

*The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2) (not volume normalized)
MPI-M ERA-20C spun-up, 1900-1915, UEA NCEP1 spun-up, 1948-1977*

What could be happening in the simulations?

Warmer steady states compared to the pre-industrial steady states

Colder steady states, compared to the OMIP spin-up states

Summary

- Internal variability and forced response: atmospheric forcing for ocean biogeochemical cycles.
→ The OMIP models are not as strongly responding as we see in CMIP6 models.
- Model's back ground mean states (i.e. spin-up states).
→ The OMIP simulations spun-up towards warm steady states, impacts on transient simulations of deoxygenation (and other ocean biogeochemical cycles)
- Uncertainties in observations (considering data coverage)
→ The limited data coverage introduce uncertainties, still the models underestimate historical deoxygenation and O₂-heat ratio (but note that observational estimates also includes uncertainties)

Ocean Spin-Up and Mean States

Supplementary Materials

Quasi Global (70°S-65°N) Integrated Ocean Heat Content

OMIP and CMIP6 Ocean Heat Content

Volcanic Eruptions

- MPI-M ERA-20C
- - Univ East Anglia NCEP1

The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2)

Quasi Global (70°S-65°N) Integrated Dissolved Oxygen *Anomaly* Inventory

OMIP and CMIP6 O₂ Inventory

Volcanic Eruptions

— MPI-M ERA-20C

- - Univ East Anglia NCEP1

The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2)

Quasi Global (70°S-65°N) Integrated Ocean Heat Content

OMIP and CMIP6 Ocean Heat Content

— MPI-M ERA-20C
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The reference is long-term mean from 1958-2009 (1968-2015 for OMIP2)

Warmer steady states compared to the pre-industrial steady states

- Long-term pre-industrial control simulations, achieve steady states & **pre-industrial conditions**.
- Ocean model spin-up, **with pre-industrial forcing** (suggestion: forcing from coupled simulations?).
- Ocean modeling community: suggest climatically neutral forcing + **pre-industrial forcing in addition**.